

TESTING AND COMPARISON OF ENERGY ABSORPTION FOR CRASH TUBES WITH DIFFERENT FIBRE ARCHITECTURES AND MATRICES

Sindy Engel-Watzek¹ and Dirk Lukaszewicz¹

¹Total Vehicle Architecture and Integration, BMW AG,
Research and Innovation Center, Knorrstrasse 147, 80788 München
Email: dirk.lukaszewicz@bmw.de, web page: <http://www.bmw.com>

Keywords: Composite, Crushing, Energy Absorption, Thermoplastic, Braiding, Dynamic Testing

ABSTRACT

Passive Safety of automotive vehicles is an important design driver in overall vehicle design, which may affect vehicle weight significantly due to the structural requirements for crash energy management. Advanced composite materials, such as Carbon Fibre Reinforced Plastics (CFRP) have been demonstrated to possess superior crash properties to conventional metallic structures used today [1]. This superior performance of CFRPs is due to higher weight-specific properties with respect to stiffness and energy absorption amongst others. However, designing structures for impact energy management is very challenging, due to a lack of studies at high speeds, with similar geometries, fibre architectures and layups.

Here, rectangular CFRP crash tubes were tested under dynamic impact at speed up to 8.2m/s while the internal architecture as well as matrix material was varied systematically. The crash tubes were made from a combination of commercially available and BMW proprietary carbon fibre. The fibre architecture was then varied using braided, fibre hybrid braiding and Non-Crimp Fabric (NCF) material configurations. In addition NCF parts were made from both epoxy as well as PA66 thermoplastic matrix. Lastly, for each configuration the number of plies and the layup were varied.

The results show great promise to improve energy absorption through; 1. Use of epoxy over PA66 thermoplastic matrix material; 2. Smaller diameter geometries with higher material thickness; 3. Lower fibre areal weight materials and higher ply count and; 4. Layups with fibres predominantly oriented parallel to the impact direction. The results thus indicate a potential route forward for composite impact management structures for automotive applications.

1 INTRODUCTION

Passive Safety of automotive vehicles is an important design driver in overall vehicle design, which may affect vehicle weight significantly due to the structural requirements for crash energy management. Advanced Composite Materials, such as Carbon Fibre Reinforced Plastics (CFRP) may have superior crash properties to conventional metallic automotive structures [2]. This superior performance of CFRPs is due to higher weight-specific properties with respect to stiffness and energy absorption amongst others. Composites may thus be used to replace existing metallic crash structures to improve impact energy management while reducing the overall vehicle weight.

One of the most commonly studied structural crash energy management elements in a vehicle is the side rail. However, while most researches have been using round tubes [1,3,4] due to better properties and simpler manufacture most side rails in today's vehicles are rectangular [5]. This is due to the fact that the side rail also acts as an attachment point for multiple vehicle components, such as an engine. In addition, most research on energy absorption of composite tubes is conducted in a quasi-static test configuration while research comparing static and dynamic testing shows that properties may vary significantly [6,7]. With respect to materials many different material configurations have been studied such as material architecture [8,9], fibre type [10], and matrix type [4]. However, most of the time it is

difficult to directly compare data from different sources due to minor differences in material architecture and test configuration.

Consequently, there is a significant gap in the understanding of the crash behaviour of CFRP tubes with rectangular geometry undergoing dynamic deformation. In addition, the impact of different design decisions, such as material architecture, matrix material and layup is difficult to relate directly making it difficult to design composite crash structures for a real vehicle application. This papers aims to address this by conducting a thorough study of rectangular CFRP crash tubes under dynamic impact.

2 SPECIMEN DESCRIPTION AND TESTING

In total four sets of studies were conducted, two sets with braided material configurations and epoxy matrices and another two using NCF material configurations with either epoxy or PA 66 thermoplastic matrices. Examples for the respective material configurations are shown in Figure 1a for NCF material and in Figure 1b for the braided material configuration. Due to restrictions arising from the braiding process the braiding yarns for the braided specimens were Toho Tenax HTS 40 carbon fibre. BMW proprietary 50k carbon fibre was used for the 0 deg axial fibres for the braided specimens. Epoxy/NCF specimens were made from Toho Tenax STS 40 fibres for the ± 45 deg orientation, while the fibres in the 0deg orientation were again 50k BMW proprietary fibre. For the PA 66 thermoplastic specimens the fibres were Zoltek carbon fibres. The specimen was rectangular with a height of 140mm and width varied between 70 and 130mm. The corner radii were varied between 15 and 25mm. All specimens were 400 mm long. In addition a 45 deg chamfer trigger with 1 mm fillet was used, see Figure 2. The height and width were varied in range between 70 and 140 mm, the corner radii were varied between 15 and 25 mm.

Figure 1a) Example of a Non-Crimp Fabric (NCF) ply with principal material orientation highlighted in white, and b) example of a braided ply with principal material orientations

Figure 2: Example of the specimen geometry used showing trigger and principle geometry [11].

In addition to geometric variations the amount of fibres in the axial direction and the number of layers was varied. The axial fraction A , was calculated using the total fibre areal weight of the axial fibres, wf_A compared to the total fibre areal weight of entire layup, wf_L described in percent of the layup or material thickness.

$$A = \frac{wf_A}{wf_L} \cdot 100 \quad (1)$$

Since the layup had to be described consistently for braided and NCF layup the fibres were oriented in a $(\theta, 0, \theta)n$ layup with θ being the orientation of the transverse fibres and n being the ply count. The ply count n was varied between 2 and 4 for braided material. For the NCF specimens the layup was chosen such that the area weight was the same for each direction in the NCF and braided material configuration. As a consequence the above base layup from the braided configuration was reproduced in NCF using three layers per number of layers n . It should be noted that while the transverse fibres in the braided material configuration were crimped this was not the case for the NCF material configuration. This crimp in the braid thickness direction has been demonstrated to improve energy absorption [8]. Equally, NCF specimens were manufactured from lower fibre areal weight materials than braided specimens, resulting in higher ply counts for the same overall material thickness which has also been demonstrated to improve energy absorption [6,12].

Furthermore, a nylon stitching yarn was present in each ply of the NCF material but not in the braided material configuration. A summary of the different material configurations is presented in Table 1. An overview of the specimen configurations is given in Table 2 for test programs A, C and D. Table 3 gives an overview of the specimen configurations for test program B.

2.1 SPECIMEN MANUFACTURE

Due to the differences in fibre architecture the specimens were manufactured using a number of different manufacturing routes. Specimens for test program “A” and “B” were braided onto a foam core. The filler yarns were 50k carbon fibres while the braiding yarns were carbon fibres in 12k and 24k rovings. The different fibre-types were necessary to be able to alter the fraction of fibres in axial and transverse direction within the desired range. Foam cores were made from Styrodur material, which was cut to shape using hot wire cutting. After braiding each specimen was wrapped in peel ply to prevent distortion of the fibres in the tool and to simplify demoulding. The specimen was then placed in a closed steel mould where it was infused with epoxy resin and hardener using low-pressure resin-transfer moulding (RTM). After infusion the core was removed to prevent deformation of the specimen due to thermal expansion of the core. The specimens were cured at 60°C for 4 hours and another 4 hours at 95°C to fully cure all specimens. Then the peel ply was removed. All specimens had a nominal fibre volume fraction of 50%. Specimens for test program “C” were manufactured by cutting the dry plies to size and producing stacks of the desired layups. Those stacks were wrapped around an inflatable core stabilized with grit.

Table 1: Overview of the conducted test programs.

		Test Program			
		A	B	C	D
Material Configuration	-	Braiding	Braiding	NCF	NCF
Matrix	-	Epoxy	Epoxy	Epoxy	PA66
Width	[mm]	140	70	140	140
Height	[mm]	70; 100; 130	70; 100; 130	70; 100; 130	70; 100; 130
Corner radii	[mm]	15; 20; 25	15	15; 20; 25	15; 20; 25
Axial Fraction	[%]	28; 44; 60	28; 44; 60	28; 44; 60	28; 44; 60
Transverse Fibres Orientation	[deg]	45	45; 60; 75	45	45
Ply Count n	$[(\theta, 0, \theta)n]$	2; 3; 4	2; 3; 4	2; 3; 4	2; 3; 4

Table 2: Generic specimen labelling for test programs A, C and D.

Specimen	Height [mm]	Width [mm]	Radius [mm]	Axial Fibre Fraction [%]	Ply Count n [[θ , 0, θ] n]
1	140	70	15	28	2
2	140	70	25	28	2
3	140	70	15	60	2
4	140	70	25	60	2
5	140	70	15	28	4
6	140	70	25	28	4
7	140	70	15	60	4
8	140	70	25	60	4
9	140	130	15	28	2
10	140	130	25	28	2
11	140	130	15	60	2
12	140	130	25	60	2
13	140	130	15	28	4
14	140	130	25	28	4
15	140	130	15	60	4
16	140	130	25	60	4
0	140	100	20	44	3

Table 3: Generic specimen labelling for test programs B where the fibre orientation was varied and the corner radius was kept at $r = 15\text{mm}$.

Specimen	Height [mm]	Width [mm]	Fibre Angle [deg]	Axial Fibre Fraction [%]	Ply Count n [[θ , 0, θ] n]
1	70	70	45	60	2
2	70	140	45	60	2
3	70	70	75	60	2
4	70	140	75	60	2
5	70	70	45	80	2
6	70	140	45	80	2
7	70	70	75	80	2
8	70	140	75	80	2
9	70	70	45	60	4
10	70	140	45	60	4
11	70	70	75	60	4
12	70	140	75	60	4
13	70	70	45	80	4
14	70	140	45	80	4
15	70	70	75	80	4
16	70	140	75	80	4
0	70	105	60	70	3

Peel ply was then again wrapped around each specimen. Specimens were then infused using RTM. Due to the lack of crimp and higher ply counts elevated infusion pressures were used. Specimens were then again tempered at 60°C for 4 hours and another 4 hours at 95°C.

Thermoplastic specimens for test program “D” were manufactured from pre-impregnated tape material. Plies were cut and stacked to produce the desired layup. The complete stack was then placed flat into the lower half of an aluminium mould. An inflatable core was then laid in and the material was draped around the core and into the lower mould. Then, the tool was closed and heated while the core was kept under controlled pressure to consolidate the tapes.

2.2 EXPERIMENTAL TESTING

Testing was conducted using a sled configuration for dynamic impact as shown in Figure 3. The samples were machined flat and a chamfer trigger was machined onto the side facing the impactor. The specimen was glued into a base-plate using Betamate adhesive and wrapped in glass cloth to avoid undesired structural failure on the backside. The back plate was then bolted onto a piezo-electric load cell.

The specimen was then impacted at a test speed of 8.2 m/s and the test mass was varied to ensure a maximum deformation of 100-300 mm for each specimen. Lower deformation would prevent stabilisation of failure, higher deformation length could damage the impact setup and lead to incomplete energy absorption by the specimen. During testing the axial force as a function of time was recorded at the base plate. Further, high-speed imaging was used to correlate the measured force-time curve to specific failure modes. The velocity of the impactor was measured using a laser device. All specimens were optically inspected after testing to document their failure modes. An example of a typical force-displacement result for a composite crush tube is shown in Figure 4. It can be seen that after an initial peak load, which may be attributed to failure initiation, composite tubes exhibit a highly uniform deformation behaviour.

Filtering was used to reduce the noise of the test data. Here all data were filtered using a Butterworth 4-pole phaseless digital filter according to SAE J211 [13] with a channel frequency class of 180. The test results were analysed for their specific energy absorption (SEA) and sustained crush stress (SCS). The two metrics were calculated according to [1]:

$$SEA = \frac{W}{\rho A \delta} = \frac{\int_0^{\delta} F d\delta}{\rho A \delta} \quad (1)$$

and

$$SCS = \frac{F_{Mean}}{A} \quad (2)$$

Figure 3: Impact test configuration [11].

SEA was chosen as a performance metric because it allows the comparison of specimens irrespective of size and weight. Here, SEA was calculated with the integral of the force/displacement curve, however the initial force peak was removed from the result. This is due to the fact that the initial peak may be interpreted as an artefact of the triggering method and is much more pronounced in dynamic testing, than in static testing. SCS was chosen because it represents a direct input for numerical simulation of crash structures, for example using Finite Element Methods (FEM). Each test was repeated at least twice, this was generally considered acceptable as prior research had demonstrated the high reproducibility of composite impact experiments [14]. The results were then averaged.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Figure 5 shows an image sequence for the deformation of a composite tube during dynamic testing. The continuous formation of debris due to the deformation of the composite material can be seen. This is in contrast to the typically more ductile concertina folding deformation found in metallic structures

This Figure also illustrates the high degree of load uniformity and significant drop between peak and mean load often observed in composite specimens. The test results for the specimens “A”, “C” and “D”, where the geometry and axial fibre fraction was varied are summarized in Figure 6 for the SEA results and in Figure 7 for the SCS results. Test results for specimens “B”, where the geometry, axial fibre fraction and layup were varied are summarized in Figure 8 for the SEA results and in Figure 9 for the SCS results. The result for test program “B” specimen 14 was removed, because the data were considered inconsistent. Similarly, the SCS results for test program “A” specimen 0 were omitted.

Generally speaking the experimentally measured SEA values range from 22 kJ/ to 67 kJ/kg, which is generally lower than most results in the literature for comparable systems. One explanation could be the analysis method, which omits the peak load from the SEA analysis. Another explanation could simply be the fact that testing was conducted in a dynamic test configuration which has been reported in the literature to yield lower SEA results.

When analysing the results of the test program for the impact of material thickness it can be seen that for all test programs the SEA generally increases with increasing wall thickness and this has been previously reported in the literature as well for the ratio of wall thickness to specimen diameter t/D .

Figure 4: Example of a force-displacement curve from a dynamic impact test on a composite tube.

Figure 5: Deformation sequence during dynamic testing of a crush specimen [11].

Figure 6: Overview of the crush test results for specific energy absorption (SEA) for the test specimens with fixed layup.

Figure 7: Overview of the crush test results for specific crush stress (SCS) for the test specimens with fixed layup.

Figure 8: Overview of the crush test results for specific energy absorption (SEA) for the test specimens with variable layup and axial fibre fraction.

Figure 9: Overview of the crush test results for specific crush stress (SCS) for the test specimens with variable layup and axial fibre fraction.

For the remaining variables the data show significant differences between the test programs. When comparing the epoxy specimen with braided material configuration “A” and NCF “B” it can be seen that nominally identical specimens exhibit up to 75% higher SEA for NCF material and up to 102% higher SCS with an average SEA increase of 42% and SCS increase of 53%.

Similarly, Thermoplastic NCF specimens “C” exhibit SEA values up to 69% higher than specimens “A” and an increase in SCS of up to 82% with an average SEA increase of 31% and SCS increase of 41%. This result indicates that higher ply count material, such as NCF are beneficial for energy absorption. In addition this raises questions about the conclusion in some literature sources, that crimped materials also increase SEA.

When comparing NCF specimens with either epoxy or thermoplastic matrix it can be seen that SEA and SCS are both 5% lower on average for the thermoplastic matrix. However, the results are more varied and range from 22% reduction to 50% increase in SEA for thermoplastic matrices. Similarly, the SCS results vary from 28% reduction to 57% increase for thermoplastic material. This shows that for the specimens studied epoxy matrices exhibit higher SEA than PA 66 matrix, however the correct choice of matrix material is not as clear as expected and would warrant further research as the variability in the thermoplastic specimens was high.

Another interesting result is the fact that the corner radii of the investigated specimens show no clear trend with respect to SEA. This contradicts previous findings from [15] amongst others who reported a correlation between SEA and corner geometries due to the stiffening effect these will have on the geometry. However, this should be carefully evaluated to avoid simply increasing the contact area and reducing the aspect ratio of the specimen, both of which have also been shown to improve SEA to some extent. A direct comparison between the two braided/epoxy material configurations shows that SEA and SCS increase with increasing axial fibre fraction and layup angle which has also been observed for other braided specimens including glass/carbon hybrid braiding [11].

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors would like to thank their colleagues at BMW and Christian Bögle in particular for their support and contribution. We would also like to express our gratitude to the Fraunhofer EMI for conducting the dynamic impact experiments.

REFERENCES

- [1] Lukaszewicz DH-JA. Automotive Composite Structures for Crashworthiness. Elmarakbi A (ed). In: *Advanced Composite Materials for Automotive Applications: Structural Integrity and Crashworthiness*. Chichester, United Kingdom: Wiley, 2013.
- [2] Hull D. A unified approach to progressive crushing of fibre-reinforced composite tubes. *Comp Sci Tech*. 1991;40:377-421.
- [3] Farley GL, Wolterman, R.L, Kennedy JM. The effects of crushing surface roughness on the crushing characteristics of composite tubes. *J Am Helicopter Soc*. 1992;July:53-60.
- [4] Hamada H, Coppola JC, Hull D, Maekawa Z, Sato H. Comparison of energy absorption of carbon/epoxy and carbon/PEEK composite tubes. *Composites*. 1992;23(4):245-52.
- [5] Engel S, Boegle C, Majamaeki J, Lukaszewicz DH-JA, Moeller F. Experimental investigation of composite structures during dynamic impact. In: *ECCM 15*. Venice, Italy: 2012.
- [6] Karbhari VM, Haller JE. Rate and architecture effects on progressive crush of braided tubes. *Comp Struct*. 1998;43(2):93-108.
- [7] Mamalis AG, Manolakos DE, Demosthenous GA, Ioannidis MB. Analytical modelling of the static and dynamic axial collapse of thin-walled fibreglass composite conical shells. *Int J Impact Eng*. 1997;19(5):477-92.
- [8] Bisagni C, Di Pietro G, Frascini L, Terletti D. Progressive crushing of fiber-reinforced composite structural components of a Formula One racing car. *Comp Struct*. 2005;60(4):391-402.
- [9] Kim J-S, Yoon H-J, Shin K-B. A study on crushing behaviors of composite circular tubes with different reinforcing fibers. *Int J Impact Eng*. 2011;38(4):198-207.
- [10] Chiu C-H, Tsai K-H, Huang WJ. Crush-failure modes of 2D triaxially braided hybrid composite tubes. *Comp Sci Tech*. 1999;59:1713-23.
- [11] Lukaszewicz D. *Crash Eigenschaften von CFK-Strukturen im Automobilbau*. VDI "Fahrzeugsicherheit". Berlin: VDI, 2013.
- [12] Schultz MR. *Energy absorption capacity of graphite-epoxy composites tubes*. Virginia Polytechnic Institute and State University, 1998.
- [13] SAE J211-1, Instrumentation for impact test - Part 1 - Electronic Instrumentation, 1995.
- [14] Bisagni C. Experimental investigation of the collapse modes and energy absorption characteristics of composite tubes. 2009;14(4).
- [15] Feraboli P, Wade B, Deleoa F, Rassaian M. Crush energy absorption of composite channel section specimens. *Comp A*. 2009;40(8):1248 - 56.